

PATENT TROLLS AND SCHUMPETER'S CREATIVE DESTRUCTION

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There is no doubt that intellectual property should be protected because it is particularly vulnerable to "stealing". However, under the law for some time this "protection" is used to make profit by "Not Practicing Entities" - (the NPE's) also called Patent Trolls. Activity of Patent Trolls companies can significantly contribute to inhibit the diffusion process in the knowledge based economy. As Schumpeter recognized the concept of dynamic capitalism was doomed to fail, because the increased efficiency of the capitalist enterprise would lead to monopolistic structures and loss of the idea of entrepreneurship. Today we may risk statement that over-regulation in the field of patent protection in conjunction with the unfair practices of companies Patent Trolls may lead to stop the development of Knowledge Based Economy. The purpose of this article is to describe the abuse of intellectual property rights protection for companies that are "Non-Practicing Entities" (Patent Trolls) in the light of J.A. Schumpeter's creative destruction concept.

Patent Trolls, NPE's, Non-Performing Entity, creative destruction, innovation.

1. Patent Trolls in Knowledge Based Economy

Nowadays the economies are increasingly based on knowledge and information. Knowledge is now recognized as the main driver of productivity and economic growth, leading to a new focus on the role of information, technology and learning in economic performance. The term "Knowledge Based Economy" stems from this fuller recognition of the place of knowledge and technology in modern economies.

The modern economies are more strongly dependent on the creation, distribution and use of knowledge than ever before. Productivity and employment are expanding fastest in high-technology industries than in any other sector. In the past decade, the high-technology share of manufacturing production and exports has more than doubled, to reach 20-25 per cent. Knowledge-intensive service sectors, are growing even faster. Indeed, it is estimated that more than 50 per cent of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in the major modern economies is now "knowledge-based" [1]. Some authors (Dosi, Freeman, Nelson, Rosenberg, Soete, Winter, Verspagen) suggest that the new set of basic innovations and globalization could constitute the start of a new technological paradigm of the Schumpeter's "fifth long wave" which is called "Information age" or "Knowledge Based Economy age", which has started in the 90s. The fifth wave of technology innovation be-

gan with the supply of cheap computers, digital computer networks and the Internet. This wave mainly depends on globalization of the economy, information systems which have evolutionary changed the business environment and reduced business distance barriers. The fifth wave was caused by the rapid development of new technologies based on knowledge and information. Typical sectors associated with the fifth wave are: aerospace, automotive, biotechnology, computers, consumption products, cybernetics, electronics, electrical engineering, e-commerce, financial services, hardware, information technology, logistics, medical engineering, medical services, mobile communication, media, nanotechnology, networking, nuclear physics, pharmaceuticals, robotics, semiconductors, software, and telecommunications. Thus it can be concluded the essential attribute of Schumpeterian "long wave" concept is the incorporation of entrepreneurship, technological progress and process of innovations. We can therefore assume that "Schumpeter's fifth wave" is equal to the "Knowledge Based Economy" era.

Processes that occurred in the past two decades, associated with the development of globalization and computerization are almost impossible to reverse. Knowledge and information has now become not just part of doing business, but it is the primary value driver of the company. In this "New Economy" era intellectual property rights has become crucial in business strategy building. No less significant function also fulfills the patent. New conditions of creating entrepreneurship led to the phenomenon of using laws protecting of intellectual property to make profit. Patents play an important role in Knowledge Based Economies, especially in sectors associated with the fifth wave; to name a few.

However what is most interesting is fact that firms increasingly file patents as a key strategic driver to compete on the markets [2]. This development is a challenge for the patent systems, and the growing lack of transparency creates legal uncertainty for numerous firms. During the past years, analysis have provided evidence for a strong concentration of patent files which in some technological fields even yields patent thickets, a web of overlapping patents that protect similar innovations [3].

The essence of a patent is linked with the concept of innovation and invention, which are the foundation of a Knowledge Based Economy. Recently there is noticeable increased activity of so-called Patent Trolls. Patent Trolls are also called NPE's (Non Practicing Entities). The company is NPE's, when it "does not practice" with the ownership of certain patent rights. NPE's is the company that is using legal norms to generate financial profits only from the ownership of certain patents. Other terms (besides Patent Troll) used for NPE's in the literature are: patent marketer, patent dealer, patent shark or a comparison to Goliath and David [5][6]. In the paper the concept of Patent Troll and NPE's are used synonymously. According to publicly available data on the operations of the type of NPE's, since 1985 NPE's have been involved in 11 thousand disputes with approximately 32 thousand companies. Lawsuits from NPE's have become very common in recent years. In 2013 Patent Trolls sued about 3 thousand companies. Furthermore number of lawsuits from NPE's companies in 2004-2013 period grew over thirteen times (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 Number of lawsuits from Patent Trolls companies in 2004-2013

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The purpose of a lawsuit from the Patent Troll is to get compensation from infringing a patent held by the NPE's. The costs of patent claims coming from NPE's companies (only to companies listed on the American Stock Exchange) in 2011 amounted to approximately 80 billion USD [4]. Patent Trolls mainly engaged in the redemption of old or registration new patents. Patent Troll sue to obtain compensation from the infringer to the patent held by the Patent Troll. Estimated time of trial with NPE's is approximately 30 months. The average cost of a license that the court admitted for Patent Troll is about 7.5 million USD. The average cost of a license negotiated out of court under a settlement with Patent Troll is 29.75 million USD. For companies costs associated with the defense of the lawsuit in a single process is about 800 thousand USD for startup's and about 7.9 million USD for companies whose annual revenues exceed 50 billion USD. The chances of "winning" by NPE's are approximately 24%, regardless of whether it is the result of a settlement, negotiation, winning in court, or winning on appeal [7]. According to above It can be concluded that activity as a Patent Troll is a profitable business. It is a business strategy based on the creative use of existing legal norms to gain extraordinary profits.

Patent Troll begin their activity at the time when the product technology (which is the carrier of intellectual property becomes a particular undertaking primary) the most important and when incurred for the product expenditures are large enough that the unconscious entrepreneur faces the dilemma of either withdrawn from the market recently introduced product, or "pay " NPE's compensation. From the point of view of the entrepreneur "offending" the resignation of the product cost (unpaid Troll) it costs:

- loss of potential future earnings,
- investment in alternative technologies that increase with the phase of the implementation technology.

In most cases, when a Patent Troll directs its claim, the company has violated the rights of intellectual property and decides not to withdraw the product from the market.

Today's Patent Trolls are well prepared for law battle companies. For example biggest NPE – „Intellectual Ventures” has portfolio consisting of 25 thousand patents. Second in line “Interdigital” has 3,5 thousand patents. It is a perfect weapon to fight with the biggest global companies (see Table 1.).

Table 1 Number of lawsuits from Patent Trolls to the largest companies in the world in 2009-2013

No.	Company	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	total
1	Google*	19	22	66	43	42	192
2	Apple	27	35	43	44	42	191
3	Samsung	12	22	42	37	38	151
4	HP	27	37	33	20	33	150
5	AT&T	16	22	34	24	51	147
6	Dell	28	24	35	21	32	140
7	Amazon.com	14	20	39	22	31	126
8	Sony	24	21	31	23	26	125
9	Verizon	14	17	26	25	42	124
10	LG	12	24	28	25	27	116

* including lawsuits by the company Motorola Mobility

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Patent Trolls activity in the Knowledge Based Economy is harmful in many ways: it harms sued companies that need to spend more and more money on legal services, and need to be ready to pay a not inconsiderable amounts of compensation or "settlement"; it also harms customers of suited firms, since the costs of lawsuits from Patent Trolls are later hidden in the prices of products or services; it harms the economy because lawsuits from NPE's impede innovation process. What's more, Patent Trolls behaviors are imitated by other companies to maintain its competitive position.

2. Creative Destruction versus protection of intellectual property rights

The concepts of innovation and entrepreneurship are probably Schumpeter's most distinctive contributions to economics [8]. According to Schumpeter's "first innovation theory" the entrepreneur-innovator is the entity that builds its competitive advantage in the market through the implementation of innovation in the economy first. Later in "second innovation theory" Schumpeter's entrepreneur has less individualistic character. Schumpeter clearly says that the entrepreneur is not necessarily one person (which is quite a radical departure from earlier theories of innovation where the entrepreneur was a prominent individualist). An entrepreneur may even be a country or its agenda. The cause of the evolution of Schumpeter previews were direct observation of the economic life of the United States [9].

Schumpeter believed innovation is the center of economic change causing "gales of creative destruction". "Creative destruction" is a term created by Schumpeter in "Capitalism, Socialism and Democracy" published in 1942. It is a "process of industrial mutation

that incessantly revolutionizes the economic structure from within, incessantly destroying the old one, incessantly creating a new one". He also proposed a taxonomy of technological change based on three stages: invention, innovation and diffusion [10].

Schumpeter actually argued that innovation leads to temporary monopoly, not that monopoly leads to innovation. Furthermore, Schumpeter's purpose of analysis of firms was not answering the question: how firms innovate or a defense of monopolies and oligopolies. It was rather an evolutionary analysis of how technology in a specific institutional context changes the structure of the economy and eventually changes the institutional context [11]. The crucial is "temporary monopoly" statement - patent extends its owners monopoly maximum for twenty years. That is the time when technological change based on three stages: invention, innovation and diffusion is disrupted.

Many writers have pointed that Schumpeter's ideas of "creative destruction" underlying the modern emphasis on technological change. However, it is worth noting that Schumpeter did not reserve the term for just technological change. For him, it was useful for analyzing many areas of the economy. As he noted: "This concept covers the following five cases: (1) The introduction of a new good – that is one with which consumers are not yet familiar – or of a new quality of a good. (2) The introduction of a new method of production, that is one not yet tested by experience in the branch of manufacture concerned, which need by no means be founded upon a discovery scientifically new, and can also exist in a new way of handling a commodity commercially. (3) The opening of a new market, that is a market into which the particular branch of manufacture of the country in question has not previously entered, whether or not this market has existed before. (4) The conquest of a new source of supply of raw materials or half-manufactured goods, again irrespective of whether this source already exists or whether it has first to be created. (5) The carrying out of the new organization of any industry, like the creation of a monopoly position (for example through trustification) or the breaking up of a monopoly position" [12].

The role of monopoly in the economy stems from the innovation processes. According to Schumpeter, innovation is divided into five types [12].:

1. The launch of a new product or a new species of already known product.
2. An application of new methods of production or sales (not yet proven in the industry) of a product.
3. The opening of a new market (the market for which a branch of the industry was not yet represented).
4. The acquiring of new sources of supply of raw material or semi-finished goods.
5. The new industry structure such as the creation or destruction of a monopoly position.

Monopoly position in the economy is the position of the company, which first has obtained a competitive advantage as a result of the implementation of the innovation. This is followed by a process of creative destruction and innovation. Then in the process of diffusion innovation becomes available to other companies. The fifth point of the above types of Schumpeter's innovation is about creating a monopoly as a result of the imple-

mentation of the innovation or destruction of a monopoly position as a result of the emergence of the process of creative destruction. In other words, according to Schumpeter monopoly position in the market is temporary until the innovation will not spread out enough, what in consequences will force the company to seek another innovation as a source of competitive advantage.

Schumpeter in 1946 viewed the entrepreneur as a creator of disequilibrium in the marketplace, who is able to recognize and exploit market opportunities before others and reaps the profits for his acts of creative destruction. Though there is no consensus amongst scholars on how to define the terms "entrepreneur" and "entrepreneurship", the contemporary literature largely shares the understanding that entrepreneurship entails a process which starts with the discovery of an opportunity that can be capitalized on by *creating a new organization* [13].

A particularly important Schumpeter's statement was (in the context of Patent Trolls activity) that the primary phase of the invention or innovation has less impact on the economy than the phase diffusion and imitation. Macroeconomic effects of any fundamental innovations are hardly noticeable in the first few years, and even longer. Important from the economic growth, investment and employment point of view is not innovation, but rather the diffusion of innovation - the period when followers begin to realize the potential gains from new product or service [14]. The activities of Patent Trolls is stopping the process of diffusion and imitation in the economy.

Schumpeter recognized that the concept of dynamic capitalism was doomed to fail, because the increased efficiency of the capitalist enterprise would lead to long-term monopolistic structures and loss of the idea of entrepreneurship. Today we may state that over-regulation in the field of patent protection in conjunction with the unfair practices of NPE's can lead also to halt the development of the capitalist economy.

Activity of Patent Trolls companies can significantly contribute to inhibit the diffusion process in the Knowledge Based Economy. And as Schumpeter recognized that the concept of dynamic capitalism was doomed to fail, because the increased efficiency of the capitalist enterprise would lead to monopolistic structures and loss of the idea of entrepreneurship, so today we may risk statement that over-regulation in the field of patent protection in conjunction with the unfair practices of companies Patent Trolls may lead to stop the development of Knowledge Based Economy.

3 Conclusions

Schumpeter believed that the presence of discrete and "revolutionary" changes in the economy is the core of "economic development" that "kicks" the economy out of its static mode ("circular flow") and sets it on a dynamic growth path. What is most important three decades later, in his work "Capitalism, Socialism, and Democracy" (1942) [15], Schumpeter recognized that the concept of dynamic capitalism was condemned to failure because the increased efficiency of the capitalist enterprise would lead to monopolistic structures and it will cause loss of the idea of entrepreneurship. This statement is crucial

for the purpose of this paper. We can therefore conclude that protection of intellectual property rights by patents and licenses simulates monopoly conditions for maximum twenty years for patent (license) owner. During this time entrepreneurial and innovation processes are being stopped.

Without a doubt, the property right must be protected. Ownership of intellectual property should be protected as well. However there is a major barrier blocking the formation of innovation in the economy, involving the utilization of the intellectual property laws to generate profit. Schumpeter arguing that the entrepreneur to generate profit must implement innovations in the economy, probably did not mean "ingenuity" that show the Patent Trolls using a rule of law to reap the benefits of this title. Patents and NPE's activity is Knowledge Based Economy "brake". What is interesting now, with the problems caused by overgrowth of bureaucracy in terms of patent protection, we will fight through regulations causing further overregulation. This vicious circle is in contradiction to the assumptions of the J. A. Schumpeter's theory of innovation.

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